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Abstract: This article discusses the role of electronic patterns in sewing products, their technological, aesthetic and functional significance. It is noted that with the help of electronic patterns, it is possible to add not only artistic decoration to clothes, but also technical capabilities - functions such as LED lighting, heating, touch control. The article analyzes the application of electronic patterns in the fields of fashion, medicine, sports, transport and "smart clothing", as well as technical and mechanical problems encountered in the process of their development.

Keywords: electronic patterns, sewing products, digital patterning, smart clothes, technological design, LED elements, sensor systems, fashion industry, technical problems, electromagnetic compatibility, interactive textiles, energy source, digital technologies, automated sewing machines, functional clothes.

Nowadays, the role of electronic patterns in sewing is relevant, and electronic pattern technologies can be used to add complex, aesthetic, and functional elements to sewing products. These patterns are usually created using computers and are directly applied to the production process.

The appearance, design, and aesthetics of today's clothing play an important role. The appearance of a garment is enriched through intricate and detailed patterns. Usually it is used as an important tool in creating electronic patterns, combining embroidery techniques, automated sewing machines, and digital patterning technologies.

Electronic patterns bring a dual function to clothing: aesthetic appearance and technical capabilities (e.g. LED lighting, heating, sensors).

For example, if a pattern placed on clothing contains a lighting LED element, the pattern is also decorative, but it also functions as lighting.

Electronic patterns are considered to be durable within clothing: the electrical connection must not be interrupted when the pattern is bent, washed, or the garment is deformed. For example, electronic paths can be created by embroidering with "liquid metal" threads. Such patterns implement electrical connections and communication protocols within the pattern, and maintain their functionality even when the garment is washed.

Electronic patterns can play a major role in the following areas:

- **Clothing and fashion:** interactive patterns (LEDs, lights, color changers) on fashion clothes.
- **Health and medicine:** health monitoring through clothing, integration of heart rate sensors, body temperature, pressure sensors and other biomarker sensors.
- **Sports and fitness:** real-time monitoring and feedback through clothing with force, pressure, and motion sensors.
- **Aero- and automotive industry:** interactive textile upholstery in the cabin, heating elements, touch-sensitive lighting patterns.
- **IoT (Internet of Things) and smart clothing:** clothes communicating with each other; having electronic systems inside clothes.

Technical issues and limitations

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There are the following problems and limitations in the practical application of electronic patterns:

Stability of electrical contact quality. The resistance of the contact points on the wire and the pattern may change, and the pattern may become discontinuous as it deforms. Liquid and chemical effects during washing processes may damage the wire and pattern. Parasitic signals, signal leakage, and electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) problems may occur.

Mechanical issues. The reliability of electrical connections can be compromised by bending and twisting of the pattern and threads. **Pattern-to-fabric compatibility:** If the pattern thread is not compatible with the fabric structure, the fabric will deform. Problems with creating patterns based on 3D structures or sharp corners. **Power supply and wiring systems.** Placing small batteries or energy harvesting modules inside the garment: space and ergonomics issues. **Power transmission, power transmission via wires or contacts:** The contacts inside the pattern must be reliable.

Reliability in mass production. Each pattern must be tested for performance, the quality of the supply must be very high. Expensive threads, special threads, modules increase the cost of production. Knitting with standard machines can be difficult - special equipment is required.

Standardization and regulation: safety standards for electronic clothing, electromagnetic compatibility, hygienic requirements.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the use of electronic patterns in clothing is one of the important directions of integrating modern technologies into fashion. Electronic patterns not only enrich the aesthetic appearance of clothes, but also give them additional functional capabilities - such as lighting, heating, or health monitoring. Smart clothes created using such patterns can be widely used not only in the fashion industry, but also in the medical, sports and technical fields. At the same time, when developing electronic patterns, it is necessary to solve technical problems such as electrical connection stability, mechanical durability and ergonomics.

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